

Smooth-Profiled Microwave Filters

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The synthesis of filters/passive components following classical approaches exhibits important limitations. Just to name a few, the target frequency responses are limited to rational functions, a lumped-element circuit model is customarily used, and the resulting square-like profiles may lead to radiation and spurious effects. In the latest years, UPNA has developed different Inverse Scattering (IS) synthesis methods based on the Coupled-Mode-Theory (CMT), leading to devices with tailor-made frequency responses and smooth profiles [1-6]. These devices are ultimately better adapted, for instance, to the emerging layer-by-layer (3D) fabrication methods (such as Selective Layer Melting, SLM) in waveguide technology or to high-power payloads. This is due to their smooth profile, which could allow growing the device along its propagation axis and without supporting structures, its intrinsic robustness to manufacturing errors due to its distributed nature, and the non-presence of parallel surfaces that avoids the electron avalanche of the multipactor effect in vacuum conditions such as in space. IS synthesis methods have been also applied at UPNA to planar technologies, where the smooth profiles are very promising to reduce radiation and spurious effects in applications that need very high operation frequencies. During the conference, we will report on our group's approaches to the synthesis of filters and passive components in the microwave and millimeter-wave ranges at UPNA, for different applications and technologies.

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- [1] I. Arnedo, M. A. G. Laso, F. Falcone, D. Benito and T. Lopetegi, "A series solution for the single-mode synthesis problem based on the coupled-mode theory," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 457–466, Feb. 2008.
- [2] I. Arnedo, I. Arregui, A. Lujambio, M. Chudzik, M. A. G. Laso, and T. Lopetegi, "Synthesis of microwave filters by inverse scattering using a closed-form expression valid for rational frequency responses," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 1244–1257, May 2012.
- [3] I. Arnedo, I. Arregui, M. Chudzik, F. Teberio, A. Lujambio, D. Benito, T. Lopetegi, and M. A. G. Laso, "Direct and Exact Synthesis: Controlling the Microwaves by Means of Synthesized Passive Components with Smooth Profiles," *IEEE Microw. Mag.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 114-128, May 2015.
- [4] I. Arnedo, M. Chudzik, J. M. Percaz, I. Arregui, F. Teberio, D. Benito, T. Lopetegi, and M. A. G. Laso, "Synthesis of one-dimensional electromagnetic bandgap structures with fully controlled parameters," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 3123–3134, Sept. 2017.
- [5] J. M. Percaz, I. Arnedo, I. Arregui, F. Teberio, P. Martín-Iglesias, M. A. G. Laso, and T. Lopetegi, "General synthesis of tapered matching sections for single-mode operation using the coupled-mode theory," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 67, no. 9, pp. 3511–3526, Sept. 2019.
- [6] J. M. Percaz, J. Hussain, I. Arregui, F. Teberio, D. Benito, P. Martín-Iglesias, I. Arnedo, M. A. G. Laso, and T. Lopetegi, "Synthesis of Rectangular Waveguide Filters with Smooth Profile Oriented to Direct Metal Additive Manufacturing," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, Early Access Article, 2023.